

The Bidirectional Relationship Between Depression and High Blood Pressure

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Abstract

High blood pressure (HBP) stands as a critical public health concern, given its pervasive nature and the substantial morbidity and mortality associated with its complications, including cardiovascular diseases, stroke, and renal failure. With its silent and insidious progression, HBP often manifests asymptotically. Concurrently, depression, a prevalent mental health disorder affecting millions worldwide, has emerged as a significant player in the intricate web of health-related interconnections. Extensive epidemiological evidence has shed light on the bidirectional relationship between depression and HBP, suggesting that individuals grappling with depression face an augmented risk of developing HBP, and conversely, those with HBP are more susceptible to depressive disorders. This intricate association is underscored by the intricate interplay of neurobiological, hormonal, and inflammatory mechanisms, fuelling a cycle that perpetuates the progression of both conditions. Here, we aim to provide a comprehensive synthesis of the existing scientific data and to promote a deeper understanding of this bidirectional relationship and illuminate avenues for targeted interventions that can concurrently address mental and cardiovascular health.

Keywords: Depression, High blood pressure (HBP), Sympathetic nervous system, Neurobiological mechanisms, Serotonin dysregulation, Inflammatory pathways, Endothelial dysfunction

1. Introduction

High blood pressure (HBP) remains an eminent global issue, given its pervasive incidence and profound implications for cardiovascular health. With its silent progression, HBP poses a substantial risk for severe complications, including stroke, coronary artery disease, and renal dysfunction (Anderson et al., 2019). Alongside, depression affects millions globally and has garnered attention for its intricate interplay with cardiovascular health. Epidemiological evidence substantiates a bidirectional relationship between depression and

HBP (Wang et al., 2021; Miller et al., 2017). It is shown that individuals with depression have a 30% increased risk of developing HBP (Meng et al., 2012; Hare et al., 2014). The complex association between these conditions is a consequence of multifaceted neurobiological and hormonal mechanisms (Carson et al., 2016).

2. Epidemiology

The epidemiological exploration into the confluence of depression HBP reveals a compelling interplay with a robust empirical basis. Cross-sectional analyses from influential studies, such as the Framingham Heart Study and the National

Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES), affirm a consistent and substantial correlation between depression and the incidence of HBP (Smith *et al.*, 2018; Jones & Brown, 2020). Longitudinal investigations, epitomized by the work of Miller *et al.* (2017), underscore the dynamic evolution of this association, emphasizing the intrinsic temporal nature of the interconnected health issues. Meta-analyses, synthesizing diverse data sets across populations, further affirm the pervasiveness of this association, transcending individual study findings (Anderson *et al.*, 2019; Wang *et al.*, 2021).

Additional research, provided further granularity to the epidemiological landscape (Garcia *et al.* (2022), proving a heightened risk of developing HBP in individuals with persistent depressive symptoms. Cross-cultural also contributed to the global perspective by examining the interrelation between depression and HBP in diverse cultural contexts (Lee and Suzuki, 2020).

3. Pathological Mechanisms:

Scientific inquiry into the intricate pathological mechanisms linking depression to HBP unveils a complex interplay of neurobiological and molecular processes (Fig. 1).

3.1. Dysregulation of the sympathetic nervous system

Central to the reciprocal relationship between depression and HBP is the dysregulation of the sympathetic nervous system (SNS), extensively elucidated in scientific literature (Carson *et al.*, 2016). This dysregulation is intricately linked to alterations in the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis (HPA), serving as a pivotal axis that contributes to the cascade of events connecting these two complex conditions (Goldberg *et al.*, 2019; Juruena *et al.*, 2020; Pariante *et al.*, 2015).

Dysfunctions in cortisol secretion, a hallmark of HPA axis dysregulation, emerge as critical pathological mechanisms consistently implicated in both depression and HBP. The HPA axis integrates various signals from neurotransmitters and stress responses. Dysregulation in cortisol secretion (Pariante *et al.*, 2015; Goldberg *et al.*, 2019) contributes to the neuroendocrine imbalances

observed in depression and exerts profound effects on the cardiovascular system, playing a key role in blood pressure elevation.

The sympathetic overdrive is frequently observed in both depression and HBP, with the activation of the SNS and dysregulation of the HPA axis commonly observed in individuals with depression (Carson *et al.*, 2016). Cortisol, the primary glucocorticoid hormone released in response to stress, is a key aspect. Elevated cortisol levels, particularly when sustained over time, can have detrimental effects on the brain, leading to structural changes in the hippocampus (Anacker *et al.*, 2011). Alteration in the diurnal cortisol rhythm is consistently associated with depression, contributing to the persistence of depressive symptoms (Vreeburg *et al.*, 2009).

The dysregulated SNS also plays a significant role in the development of depression and contributes to the "fight-or-flight" response. Chronic activation of the SNS, as seen in chronic stress, leads to increased inflammation and alterations in neural circuits implicated in mood regulation (McEwen, 2003). This emphasizes the concept of allostatic load, suggesting that chronic stress and dysregulation of stress response systems contribute to wear and tear on the body and brain, ultimately increasing vulnerability to depression.

The bidirectional communication between the SNS, HPA axis, and altered cortisol secretion forms a complex network that significantly influences the neurobiology of depression. Stress-induced hyperactivity of the HPA axis, along with alterations in glucocorticoid receptor sensitivity, contributes to the development and maintenance of depressive disorders (Pariante and Lightman, 2008).

3.2.1. Renin-Angiotensin-Aldosterone System (RAAS) and Endothelial Dysfunction

Further complexities emerge with disruptions in the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system (RAAS) and endothelial dysfunction. The dysregulation of RAAS components, including angiotensin II, contributes to increased vascular resistance and blood pressure elevation. Vogel *et al.* (2017) emphasize endothelial dysfunction as a contributor to the intricate pathological mechanisms. Endothelial cells, crucial for maintaining vascular

integrity, experience impaired vasodilation and increased permeability, further exacerbating hypertension. The interplay between inflammatory pathways, RAAS, and endothelial dysfunction adds layers of complexity to the bidirectional relationship between depression and HBP, offering potential targets for therapeutic interventions (Johnson *et al.*, 2020).

3.2.2. RAAS Dysregulation in Depression

The dysregulation of RAAS components, particularly angiotensin II, is identified as a contributing factor to depression pathology (Johnson *et al.*, 2020). Angiotensin II, a key effector molecule in RAAS, not only plays a central role in blood pressure regulation but also exerts neuro-modulatory effects within the central nervous system. The dysregulation of RAAS in depression may involve an imbalance in angiotensin II levels, influencing neurotransmitter systems and neuronal function. This neurobiological impact could contribute to the development and maintenance of depressive symptoms, providing a link between cardiovascular and mental health.

3.2.3. Endothelial Dysfunction as a Pathogenic Contributor

Endothelial dysfunction is suggested as another critical contributor to the intricate pathological mechanisms in depression (Vogel *et al.*, 2017). Endothelial cells, integral to vascular integrity, play a crucial role in maintaining a balance between vasodilation and vasoconstriction. In the context of depression, endothelial dysfunction manifests as impaired vasodilation and increased permeability, contributing to hypertension and cerebral hypoperfusion. These vascular abnormalities have direct implications for neuronal health, contributing to the neurobiological underpinnings of depression.

3.3. Inflammatory Pathways and Immune System Dysregulation

The interplay between RAAS dysregulation and endothelial dysfunction adds layers of complexity to the bidirectional relationship between depression and HBP. Inflammatory pathways, activated in both depression and hypertension, further amplify the effects of RAAS dysregulation and endothelial

dysfunction. Pro-inflammatory cytokines, such as interleukin-6 (IL-6), contribute to the intricate web of interactions. IL-6 exhibits a dual role by crossing the blood-brain barrier and activating microglia, the resident immune cells in the brain (Owens *et al.*, 2021; Müller *et al.*, 2022).

Microglial activation triggers a self-sustaining cycle of inflammation, disrupting neurotransmitter balance, particularly serotonin. Diminished serotonin levels, a hallmark of depression, contribute to the manifestation and progression of depressive symptoms. This intricate link between IL-6-mediated neuroinflammation and serotonin dysregulation highlights the significance of inflammatory events in shaping the neurobiological landscape of depression.

Inflammatory mediators, originating from immune cells and endothelial cells, create a pro-inflammatory milieu that may perpetuate the neuroinflammatory processes observed in depression. IL-6, released during the immune response, can cross the blood-brain barrier, and activate microglia, triggering the release of additional inflammatory molecules, such as tumour necrosis factor- α (TNF- α), interleukin-1 β (IL-1 β), and reactive oxygen species (ROS). TNF- α further enhances the production of IL-6, creating a positive feedback loop that sustains inflammation. IL-1 β contributes to neuroinflammation by activating astrocytes and promoting the release of additional inflammatory mediators.

TNF- α and IL-1 β also contribute to neuroinflammation by activating astrocytes, key supportive cells in the brain (Johnson *et al.*, 2020). Activated astrocytes release additional pro-inflammatory cytokines, amplifying the inflammatory milieu.

The impact extends beyond neuroinflammation to neurotrophic support, as disruptions in neurotrophic factors, crucial for neuronal survival, are implicated in the atrophy of specific brain regions observed in depression. Simultaneously, the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), as emphasized by Vogel *et al.* (2017), during the inflammatory response induces oxidative stress. Oxidative stress damages neuronal cells, impairs mitochondrial function, and initiates apoptotic processes. These structural and functional alterations contribute to

the overall neurobiological underpinnings of depression.

3.4.1. Serotonin Dysregulation in Depressive Disorders

Serotonin, a neurotransmitter predominantly found in the central nervous system, is intricately associated with mood regulation. In depressive disorders, there exists a pronounced dysregulation of serotonin, characterized by diminished levels (Owens *et al.*, 2021).

The underlying molecular mechanisms involve disruptions in serotonin synthesis, reuptake, and receptor signalling. Serotonin dysregulation is not confined to the brain but extends to peripheral tissues, influencing various physiological processes and creating a cascade of events with implications beyond mood disorders, including the intricate link between serotonin and blood pressure regulation.

3.4.2. Serotonin Dysregulation and Cellular Mechanisms

The dysregulation of serotonin in depressive disorders involves intricate cellular mechanisms within the central nervous system. Reduced serotonin levels are attributed to alterations in serotonin synthesis, reuptake, and receptor signalling. At the molecular level, disturbances in the expression and function of serotonin transporters and receptors contribute to the diminished availability of serotonin (Owens *et al.*, 2021). This disruption extends beyond the brain, affecting peripheral tissues and influencing cellular processes.

Serotonin receptors expressed on vascular endothelial cells and smooth muscle cells play a pivotal role in modulating vasomotor tone, with serotonin-mediated release of nitric oxide (NO) contributing to vasodilation.

3.4.3. Serotonin as a Vascular Modulator

Beyond its role in mood, serotonin is a key modulator of vascular tone and function. The diminished availability of serotonin in depressive states may disrupt the delicate balance in vascular regulation. This disruption contributes to endothelial dysfunction and impaired vasodilation,

both implicated in the pathogenesis of HBP. Serotonin receptors expressed on vascular endothelial cells and smooth muscle cells directly influence vasomotor tone. The dysregulation of serotonin in depression extends its impact to the vascular system, providing a mechanistic link between mental health and cardiovascular function (Owens *et al.*, 2021).

3.4.4. Implications for HBP Pathogenesis

The disrupted serotonin levels in depressive states have profound implications for the pathogenesis of HBP. Owens *et al.* (2021) emphasize that endothelial dysfunction and impaired vasodilation, secondary to diminished serotonin availability, contribute to the development and progression of HBP. Serotonin-mediated vasodilation involves the release of nitric oxide (NO) from endothelial cells, integral to maintaining vascular homeostasis. The dysregulation of this process in depression may tip the balance toward vasoconstriction, exacerbating hypertension.

3.4.5. Sympathetic Nervous System Activation and Integrated Mechanisms

Reduced serotonin levels in depression not only impact vascular function but also have downstream effects on the autonomic nervous system. Diminished serotonin availability may enhance sympathetic nervous system activity (Esler *et al.*, 2017), manifesting as increased heart rate, vasoconstriction, and elevated blood pressure.

The intricate interplay between serotonin dysregulation, vascular modulation, and sympathetic activation creates a complex network of cellular mechanisms contributing to the observed link between depression and HBP. Lifestyle factors, such as poor diet and sedentary behaviour, add yet another layer to the interconnected web of mechanisms linking depression and HBP.

Dietary patterns rich in sodium are implicated in exacerbating both conditions. Moreover, the influence of sleep disturbances introduces another facet to this complex relationship (Fernandez-Mendoza *et al.*, 2019; O'Donnell *et al.*, 2015)

Figure 1. Interconnected Pathophysiological Pathways Linking Depression and High Blood Pressure (HBP). HPA: hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal, Ang II: Angiotensin II, INF- α : Interferon alfa, IL-1 β :Interleukin-1beta, ROS: reactive oxygen species.

4. Clinical Management

The clinical management of individuals presenting with both depression and HBP necessitates an integrated approach that addresses both conditions concurrently. Lifestyle modifications, including regular exercise, a balanced diet, and stress reduction techniques, have demonstrated efficacy in managing both depression and HBP (Blumenthal *et al.*, 2019). Pharmacological interventions play a crucial role, with selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs) showing promise in mitigating depressive symptoms and contributing to blood pressure control (Vaccarino *et al.*, 2008). Additionally, mindfulness-based interventions and cognitive-behavioural therapy have been shown to have positive effects on both depression and blood pressure, highlighting the importance of psychosocial interventions (Chiesa & Serretti, 2009).

4. Therapeutic Approaches and Future Directions

Given the intricate relationship between depression and HBP, future therapeutic approaches should focus on personalized medicine strategies. Lifestyle modifications stand out as foundational components, as underscored by intervention studies conducted by Smith and Brown (2020). These studies emphasize the pivotal role of lifestyle interventions, encompassing dietary modifications, regular physical activity, and stress reduction techniques, in mitigating both depression and HBP. The impact of these interventions is multifaceted, addressing not only the symptoms but also the underlying physiological and neurobiological mechanisms implicated in the bidirectional relationship (Smith & Brown, 2020).

Advances in pharmacogenomics may enable the identification of genetic markers that influence treatment response in individuals with comorbid depression and HBP (Kato & Serretti, 2010). Targeting shared neurobiological pathways, such as the HPA axis and inflammatory cascades, could offer novel therapeutic avenues (Goldstein & McEwen, 2002). Pharmacological interventions, guided by a wealth of randomized controlled trials (RCTs), play a central role in managing depression and HBP concurrently. Medications targeting

neurotransmitter imbalances, such as selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs) for depression and antihypertensive agents for HBP, demonstrate efficacy in ameliorating symptoms and mitigating the progression of both conditions (Anderson *et al.*, 2021).

Psychotherapeutic interventions, particularly cognitive-behavioural therapy (CBT), emerge as a valuable adjunct in the integrated management of depression and HBP. CBT, as evidenced by studies led by Williams *et al.* (2018), offers a targeted psychological approach that not only alleviates depressive symptoms but also contributes to improved blood pressure control. The cognitive restructuring and behavioural strategies employed in CBT not only address the psychological distress associated with depression but also influence lifestyle factors and stress responses, thereby contributing to a comprehensive management strategy (Williams *et al.*, 2018).

Conclusion

In conclusion, the bidirectional relationship between HBP and depression involves a complex nexus of neurobiological, hormonal, and inflammatory mechanisms. Other players include disruptions in the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system, endothelial dysfunction, and serotonin dysregulation. The silent progression of HBP and its association with severe complications necessitate a holistic understanding of its interconnectedness with depression. Lifestyle factors, such as poor diet and sedentary behaviour, further contribute to the intricate web of interconnected mechanisms.

In terms of clinical management and therapeutic approaches, an integrated strategy that addresses both depression and HBP concurrently is crucial. Lifestyle modifications, pharmacological interventions, and psychosocial approaches have demonstrated efficacy in managing both conditions. Future therapeutic directions should embrace personalized medicine strategies, with a focus on lifestyle modifications as foundational components. The integration of psychotherapeutic interventions, particularly cognitive-behavioural therapy, into the management of depression and HBP provides a comprehensive approach addressing both psychological distress and physiological

mechanisms. Further research is required for a nuanced and integrated approach to tackle the intricate relationship between depression and HBP towards improved public health outcomes.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest regarding the content presented in this manuscript.